

Adversarial Registration Method for Non-Rigid Brain MRI & DVF Estimation

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Abstract

Non-rigid registration of brain MRI scans is crucial in neurosurgery, ensuring accurate alignment between preoperative and intraoperative images. Brain shift caused by factors like gravity or tissue resection can deform brain tissue, disrupting this alignment and complicating precise localization of pathological areas. This study presents a deep learning-based framework for non-rigid brain MRI registration aimed at compensating intraoperative brain tissue deformations. We investigated a generative adversarial network (GAN)-based approach integrated with a deformable registration network to estimate deformation vector fields (DVFs) for accurate alignment of preoperative and intraoperative brain images. An initial 2D implementation for rapid prototyping and validation, followed by an extension to a full 3D domain to capture volumetric consistency and spatial coherence were performed. The 3D framework incorporated a combination of adversarial loss, cycle consistency, and gradient-based regularization to enhance deformation realism and anatomical fidelity. Evaluation of the proposed approach was performed using various metrics that show improved scores after registration holding promise for improving image alignment accuracy in brain shift-affected neurosurgery.

Keywords: Image registration, Medical Imaging, Artificial Intelligence, Generative Adversarial Network

1 Background and Motivation

Non-rigid registration of brain MRI scans is essential in neurosurgical contexts, where accurate alignment of preoperative and intraoperative images is crucial. Brain shift, caused by factors like gravity, cerebrospinal fluid loss, and tissue resection, disrupts this alignment, posing challenges for accurate localization of pathological tissue. Kelly et al. (1986) [1] underscored the clinical relevance of brain shift for image-guided

neurosurgery. Non-rigid registration techniques are vital for compensating such deformations and improving surgical accuracy. AI-based methods like VoxelMorph [2] have shown promise, offering fast and accurate non-rigid registration, while GANs have been explored for multimodal brain image registration (e.g., Bayer et al. [3], SymRegGAN [4]). However, their application to brain tissue deformation estimation for brain-shift compensation, especially in complex 3D-to-3D registration tasks, remains limited. This study investigates deep learning-based deformable registration techniques to enhance brain-shift registration and support data-driven clinical decisions. We first developed a 2D registration framework using a GAN [5] architecture integrated with a deformable registration network to estimate deformation vector fields (DVs) on MRI slices, demonstrating feasibility and performance. We then extended the approach to a full 3D domain, incorporating a gradient-based loss and cycle consistency adversarial loss to address volumetric registration challenges. This improved DVF estimation across volumes, enhancing alignment under realistic surgical deformations. Our results show that the 3D framework preserves anatomical continuity and improves brain structure mapping accuracy.

2 Methods & Materials

2.1 Dataset

The Brain Resection Multimodal Imaging Database (ReMIND) from The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) [6] was the primary dataset, comprising pre- and intra-operative MRI from 114 patients (2018–2022) undergoing image-guided tumor resection. For 2D training, preprocessing included center cropping, resampling, reorientation, and uniform voxel spacing, standardizing the images to $256 \times 256 \times 180$. Approximately 3000 axial slices (256×256) were extracted for training, 200 for validation, and 200 for testing, focusing on cases with visible deformation while accounting for intra- and interpatient modality variability. For 3D training, skull-stripped volumes were resampled to $80 \times 96 \times 112$, and experiments were conducted on interpatient cases with similar modalities. To augment the deformable scenarios, random elastic deformations (Figure 1) were applied, expanding the dataset to 4440 volumes for training, 600 for validation, and 400 for testing.

Fig. 1. Randomly deformed 3D volumes for training.

2.2 Training

The study employed a hybrid framework combining a CycleGAN[7] and a deformable registration network. These models trained in parallel to estimate DVFs, which

represent the spatial transformations necessary to align the preoperative and intraoperative images. The CycleGAN is utilized for adversarial and cycle-consistency training. By synthesizing realistic images, the CycleGAN facilitates better alignment by bridging the modality gap between preoperative and intraoperative MRI scans. The adversarial training encourages the generation of high-quality synthetic images, while the cycle-consistency loss ensures that the transformations are reversible and meaningful. Figure 2 (a) illustrates the basic architecture of a CycleGAN. The deformable registration network predicts the DVFs enabling the registration process by aligning the synthesized intraoperative images with the preoperative images with a spatial transformer layer. Integration of the registration framework with the GAN is represented in Figure 2(b). Along with the refinement L1 loss between the synthesized image and the preoperative image, we have added a gradient based loss based on Haar wavelet-based perceptual similarity index for image quality assessment [8]. For 2D training 2D the generator and the registration network ResUNet based architecture were used and was extended to 3D along with pretrained VGG and Resnet18 models as perceptual losses. Even though the model is capable of bidirectional registration for inference we only focus on how the preoperative image behaves similar to intraoperative image under certain deformation conditions.

Fig. 2. Architectural diagram of CycleGAN and deformable registration network integration

3 Experimental Findings

In Figure 3 the registered image represents the registration result of preoperative image to intraoperative image. Large deformations (bright colors) indicate regions where the brain has shifted more substantially, while areas with minimal color variation likely experienced less shift. The quality of the registration can be inferred by how closely the registered image aligns with the intraoperative image while keeping the image spatial content of preoperative image.

Fig. 3. 2D Registration of preoperative image to intraoperative image for 3 different cases. The third column is the registered image. The last column represents the deformation vector field

The performance of the 2D framework was evaluated using similarity metrics structural similarity index measure (SSIM), normalized mean absolute error (NMAE) and PSNR (peak to signal noise ratio) (Table 1).

Table 1. Quantitative metrics for 2D registration. The average SSIM, NMAE and PSNR before and after registration for 200 test slices are shown.

	Before Registration	After Registration
SSIM \uparrow	0.794	0.813
NMAE \downarrow	0.048	0.035
PSNR \uparrow	18.06	23.587

For quantification of the 3D registration results, metrics including SSIM, normalized mutual information (NMI), multi-scale SSIM (MS-SSIM), MAE and NMAE were used. Figure 4 and 5 show 3D registration results on augmented deformation and real deformation from the dataset. The quality of the 3D registration can be inferred by how closely the registered image aligns with the intraoperative image while maintaining the integrity of the preoperative image content. In Table 2 the quantitative results shows an increased MS-SSIM of 0.726, NMI of 0.456 after registration. The MAE and NMAE of 0.076 and 0.103 were also achieved respectively, further highlight the improvement in alignment accuracy and spatial consistency achieved by the proposed model.

Fig. 4. 3D registration results where (a) Case 1 and (b) Case 2, two different simulated intraoperative scenario and each time the registration model tries to register the preoperative image under different deformation condition. third column is the registered image.

Table 2. Quantitative metrics used to evaluate 3D volumetric registration. The average SSIM, NMAE and PSNR before and after registration for 200 test slices are shown.

	Before Registration	After Registration
SSIM \uparrow	0.4927	0.700
NMI \uparrow	0.221	0.456
MS-SSIM \uparrow	0.4824	0.726
MAE \downarrow	0.148	0.076
NMAE \downarrow	0.201	0.103

The quality of the 3D registration can be inferred by how closely the registered image aligns with the intraoperative image while maintaining the integrity of the preoperative image content. Figure 4 & 5 shows 3D registration results on augmented deformation and real deformation from the dataset. In table 2 the quantitative performance of the model can be interpreted by the increased MS-SSIM of 0.726, Normalized mutual information(NMI) of 0.456 after registration. The lower mean absolute error and normalized mean absolute error of 0.076 and 0.103 respectively, further highlight the improvement in alignment accuracy and spatial consistency achieved by the model.

Fig. 5. 3D registration results (a) with real deformation in the intraoperative image (b) with simulated deformation. In both situation the model trying it's best to align the preoperative image to intraoperative image.

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the potential of a GAN-based framework combined with a deformable registration network for non-rigid brain MRI registration, particularly for brain-shift compensation after tumor resection. The findings validate its feasibility and scalability for both 2D and 3D cases. Future work will include benchmarking against state-of-the-art methods on the same dataset and an ablation study to assess the contributions of individual components, aiming to optimize performance and enhance understanding of model behavior.

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References

1. Kelly, Patrick J., et al. "Computer-assisted stereotaxic laser resection of intra-axial brain neoplasms." *Journal of neurosurgery* 64.3 (1986): 427-439.
2. Balakrishnan, Guha, et al. "Voxelmorph: a learning framework for deformable medical image registration." *IEEE transactions on medical imaging* 38.8 (2019): 1788-1800
3. Bayer, Siming, et al. "Intraoperative imaging modalities and compensation for brain shift in tumor resection surgery." *International journal of biomedical imaging* 2017.1 (2017): 6028645.
4. Zheng, Yuanjie, et al. "SymReg-GAN: symmetric image registration with generative adversarial networks." *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 44.9 (2021): 5631-5646.
5. Reisenhofer, Rafael, et al. "A Haar wavelet-based perceptual similarity index for image quality assessment." *Signal Processing: Image Communication* 61 (2018): 33-43.